

Metal Complexes as Magic Bullet - An Overview

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Abstract:

Magic Bullet comprises of a specific synthesized drug in which metal ions play an important role. These drugs can be designed to treat and cure a specific disease by attacking on specifically diseased cells leaving aside the healthy ones, there by, increasing the efficiency of a drug. As metal ions are used since ages as immuno-modulators, they trigger the immunity, if combined with the drug. Thus, combination of drug can be chelated with metal ions, which can help to develop innovative strategies for preparing combinatorial drug, also known as "Magic Bullet" or metal complexes or mixed ligand complex in the light of the chelate hypothesis.

Key Words: Mixed Ligand Complex, Chelation, Immuno-Modulators.

Introduction:

Medicinal application of metals can be traced way back to almost 5000 years (Orvig & Abrams, 1999). Metal centers being positively charged, are favoured to bind to negatively charged biomolecules; the constituents of proteins and nucleic acids offer excellent ligands for binding to metal ions. The pharmaceutical use of metal complexes, therefore, has excellent potential. A broad array of medicinal applications of metal complexes has been investigated. Several recent reviews summarize advances in these fields (Sakurai et al, 2002; Sadler et al, 1999; Ali & van Lier, 1999; Louie & Meade, 1999; Volkert & Hoffman, 1999).

Metal ions affect the well-being of human in various ways. Several of these elements are indispensable for life and nature governs their uptake, metabolism, and excretion (Wayne, 1999). Consequently, their concentrations in a human body are compartmentalized and well defined.

When a metal ion combines with a ligand (Drug), the resulting substance is said to be a complex. If the ligand (Drug) which combine with the metal forms one or more rings with the metal, the resulting structure is said to be a metal chelate and the process is known as chelation (Wayne, 1999).

Chelation Therapy is a form of detoxication that means the chelator or chelating agent e.g. EDTA,

which actively grabs the unwanted metal ions on two sides in a claw like fashion and either inactivates it or helps remove it from the body (Kramer et al, 1996).

Ehrlich is considered to be the founder of modern drug therapy and he first coined the term Chemotherapy. In German folklore a magic bullet was one that was enchanted and could not miss its mark. Ehrlich borrowed the expression to promote his idea that a specific disease causing organism could be targeted by a specific chemical without harming human tissue (Reithmiller, 2005).

Metal complexes have found therapeutic and biomedical, analytical, synthetic applications as given below.

Therapeutic Application of Metal Complexes:

- Antibiotic Agents :- Antibiotic like Bleomycin causes DNA strand scission through formation of an intermediate metal complex requiring a metal ion cofactor such as copper or iron (Perry, 2002; Dorr & Von Hoff, 1994) for the activity in the treatment of cancer. Antibiotic drugs of the tetracycline family are chelators of Ca^{2+} and Hg^{2+} ions.
- Antiviral Agents :- It is recently discovered that Ruthenium Polyaminocarboxylate (Ru-pac complexes) possess cysteine protease inhibition activity. The ability of Ru-pac complexes to inhibit cysteine protease activity was attributed to the high affinity of the ruthenium complexes towards

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binding the SH group in the cysteine residue of the enzymes via a rapid aqua substitution reaction.

The discovery of the protease inhibition activity of Ru-pac-complexes may be of significance in developing antiviral agents in which Ru-pac complexes could act as metallo-inhibitor agents for disease progression (Chaterjee et al, 2006).

The [Ru (pac) (No)] complexes offer a number of features as nitric-oxide (NO) carriers or scavengers. (Farkas & Sovago, 2002).

- Anticancer Agents :- Cisplatin, Carboplatin are the first and second generation platinum drug respectively, which are widely used in the treatment of cancer (Kostova, 2006).

The synthesis of a tripeptide conjugate of cisplatin (Pil & Lippard, 1997) has been reported and it was suggested that similar species can be used to overcome the tumour resistance of platinum drugs. In another report the preparation of cyclopeptide metal complex conjugates has been described using the reaction between linear peptides of cysteine and [Pt (terpy)].

The high affinity of platinum for sulphur binding was used in this strategy and it was proposed that complexes of [Pt(terpy)] can be considered as both protecting and promoting groups for peptide cyclisation. (Farkas & Sovago, 2002,)

Many questions remain as to how platinum drugs carry out their antineoplastic (antitumor) activity. Scientists believe that rational design techniques will lead to better platinum containing agents that have fewer toxic side effects, overcome all types of resistance, and are efficacious in different tumour types (Kostova, 2006).

Many of the properties of the ruthenium agents tested are similar to that of platinum compounds that is, they bind to DNA (preferentially to guanine residues). Their DNA binding properties are affected by physiological sulfur ligands, such as glutathione and multiple ruthenium oxidation states and this ligand system appear to have anticancer activity. (Sava et al, 1984)

Octahedral Ru(II), and Ru(III) complexes containing ligands, such as amines, N-heterocycles and dimethyl sulfoxides exhibited various degree of biological activity including antitumour action in-vivo (Sava et al, 1984).

- Antiarthritic Agents:- Auranofin and other gold (I)

complexes are well known as antiarthritic drugs, but they also inhibit the growth of cultured tumour cells “in-vitro” and many have antimitochondrial activity (Mckeage, 2002).

Auranofin has recently become known as a potent and specific inhibitor of thioredoxin reductase (Gromer et al, 1998), an enzyme that may play an important role in the redox control of the permeability of mitochondrial membranes (Rigobello et al, 1998).

Biomedical, Synthetic and Analytical Application of Metal Complexes:

The use of metal complexes in clinical diagnostic imaging is increasing tremendously. These applications involve gamma scintigraphy, positron emission tomography (PET), Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) and metal based radiopharmaceuticals (Farkas & Sovago, 2002).

The high level expression of somatostatin receptors (SSTR) on various tumour cells has provided the molecular basis for successful use of radiolabelled octreotide, lantreotide analogs as tumour tracers in nuclear medicine (Virgolini et al, 2002). Other (non tumoral) potential indications for SSTR scintigraphy are based on an increased lymphocyte binding at sites of inflammatory or immunologic diseases such as thyroid associated eye changes (Blum et al, 2002).

A plentitude of preclinical data and clinical studies confirm their potential use in diagnosis as well as “Proof-of-principle” for therapy of cancer patients (Virgolini et al, 2002).

Compounds of Vanadium are essential nutrients for higher animals, while in humans they show insulin like properties. The biological significance of zinc finger peptides and metallothioneins have given a great impetus to further studies on the metal-ion-sulphur co-ordination (Sakurai et al, 2002).

Spectroscopic monitoring of the metal binding in zinc finger peptide is a crucial point for the structural elucidation of these complexes. It has been reported that ultraviolet Resonance Raman Spectroscopy (UVRM) can be used for simultaneous monitoring of cysteine and histidine co-ordination and promise a wide range of application. Several papers have been published on the preparation and reactivity of ferrocenyl peptides and related molecules, which can be used as redox markers and synthetic probes or for the selective monitoring of bio-molecules (Farkas & Sovago, 2002).

The biomedical applications of peptides as effective ligands for radiolabelled molecules or imaging agents received special interest. ^{99m}Tc is probably the most commonly used radioactive isotope in medical imaging, while the chemically related $^{186}\text{Re}/^{188}\text{Re}$ isotopes are promising candidates for internal radiotherapy (Blum et al, 2002).

Technetium and rhenium complexes of peptides and derivatives were studied by several research groups (Farkas & Sovago, 2002). An important development in the coordination chemistry of peptides is that peptide complexes are frequently attached to other biomolecules and the resulting species can be used as sensors or markers for analytical and biomedical purposes.

Conclusion:

Recent advances in chelation research have paved the way for targeting “magic-bullets” for chemotherapy, using different strategies and pharmacological manipulation, demonstrate significant prospects for the utilization of metal complexes as drugs and presenting a flourishing arena for medical inorganic biochemistry.

Application of new methodologies such as combinatorial drug chemistry will be beneficial for the development of newer drug. It needs to be determined to what extent toxicity of normal tissue will limit the application of chelation based therapies in clinical trials. Perhaps, chelation-based treatment will need to be tailored for each patient or group of patient and one should also take into consideration the emergence of resistance to treatment.

The great success of platinum compounds serendipitously discovered to have antitumor behaviour, should be an inspiration to scientists who continue the quest to find the “Magic-Bullet” cure for cancer, so long anticipated and so long in realization. Therefore, a combination of current conventional and chelation targeted events seems a more likely successful scenario.

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